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POLICY BRIEF

REACHING THE LAST MILE WITH KM-SCALE EARTH SYSTEM MODELS

AUTHORS
NEXTGEMS PROJECT COMMUNITY

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CONTEXT

km-scale Earth-system models

New vanguard services, products and cooperation hubs are created around km-scale earth system models. Examples are the European Union's Flagship Initiative Destination Earth (DestinE) or the recent Earth Visualisation Engines (EVE) ambition, both **pursuing essential societal goals** such as to "support future evidence-based policy-making" or "empower people to respond to the immense and urgent challenge of climate change" accordingly. However, these initiatives need targeted efforts to ensure that their outputs - of **quality and relevance**, but also costly - do not face the usability gap. Namely, despite the increases in climate data quality, evidence-based decision-making for climate action has not followed suit (1, 2, 3).

In this policy brief, we analyse the topic, to subsequently consider policy options which could support this leading-edge science to be of real and effective service to society.

BETTER FOR WHAT

Due to their ability to capture fine-scale atmospheric processes such as convective storms, local wind patterns, and precipitation more effectively, **km-scale earth system models are expected to provide better future climate information data** at different time scales, whilst also providing better understanding of extreme events (4). More precision with regards to extreme events can aid in disaster preparedness and risk mitigation efforts. These models may also offer **better long-term climate projections** by representing regional climate variations, feedback mechanisms, and interactions between different components of the Earth system (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land surface) (5, 6).

Finally, km-scale earth system models are expected to allow for an increased understanding of regional climate variability, which is crucial for **assessing the impacts of climate change on specific locations and sectors** such as agriculture, water resources, and human health (7). Assimilation of diverse observational data sets, including satellite data, ground-based measurements, and remote sensing data, can lead to improved model validation, calibration, and data assimilation techniques, reducing also uncertainty in km-scale model outputs, which is one of the concerns of more sceptical perspectives on their relevance. The opportunity of these models to be used as a **powerful visualisation device** is not to be understated, as it can bring climate change closer to non-technical users.

BETTER FOR WHOM (I)

Science

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For science and scientists themselves, km-scale modelling can bring new breakthroughs and due to the required infrastructure, it can give important technological skills to those scientists involved in developing it. However, these pioneers and, above all, early career researchers, carry the pressure from the friction between data science and climate science. The required data-intensive activities mean that the day-to-day of these scientists is spent fixing bugs and improving code (sometimes rewarding, but not always acknowledged), which can be demotivating tasks if the end-goal of improving climate science gets lost in translation and leave them prone to leave science provided that these skills are highly valued in the private sector (8). Additionally, engaging communities such as technology and science enthusiasts or other stakeholders with advanced technical skills at early stages of infrastructure development is crucial: they are the key group to see how well integration works with impact models as the linkage towards evidence-based policy-making in a myriad of sectors.

Furthermore, the development of km-scale modelling is expensive and can lead to the technological lock-in (9). What are the opportunity costs? How to allocate funding and computing resources in order to allow these advancements? Solutions go through alliances with machine learning (ML) researchers, who have become a part of the endeavour, as well as inter-institutional collaborations between research centres. And a clear responsibility distribution, should allow other initiatives - e.g. CMIP and CORDEX - to maintain their activities in spite of the resources required to push km-scale climate modelling forward.

BETTER FOR WHOM (II)

Policy

For governments, these models can be of service to multiple governance levels for impacts, adaptation, and risk management strategies but a key point is the unequal access to information and resource capacities (10). Although the latest models are not yet ready to be used, continuous engagement work with such users should ensure that the outputs of these efforts are adequate and fit for purpose. Finally, the society involves communities, companies (small-and-medium and large enterprises) and societal representatives. For small companies, access to this data can mean that their services can be made more resilient. For big companies, the integration into their business models and the offering of paid services (11). Finally, if this new infrastructure proves accessible and usable, it could accommodate access to high quality climate information to society at large.

Society

Figure, ref. 12

THE WAY FORWARD

THE FOLLOWING SET OF POLICY OPTIONS IS APPROACHED FROM A SYSTEMS-THINKING PERSPECTIVE IN WHICH ALL OPTIONS ARE SEEN AS PART OF AN INTERRELATED AND SYNERGETIC COMPLEX.

Fostering inter-institutional collaboration

As an endeavour to provide globally an equal access to km-scale climate information, this effort requests international and inter-institutional collaboration. It could hence also open new opportunities for regions and stakeholder groups with scarce resources.

Embracing transdisciplinarity

Transdisciplinarity —collaborating across academic and non-academic expertise— is increasingly essential, as seen in the EU's research funding priorities. However, climate scientists already face enough challenges without needing to master complex social systems, communication, or societal engagement. Bringing in experts from diverse disciplines, skilled in service development and user interaction, would help bridge gaps between climate science and practical applications, ensuring that km-scale climate models produce services that are both useful and widely used.

Financing: multi-stakeholder partnerships

The private sector is expected to gain greatly with this science coming forth and they can be part of financing schemes that support such efforts, including public-private partnerships.

Reducing data access barriers

Direct data access demands high technical capacities on the side of users. Access to new data should not require sophisticated technology nor high performance computing. Indirectly diminishing the barriers to data access means working towards open private-public data protocols, standards and a new era of data sharing. Moreover, capacity building efforts should start from early-phases, allowing users to provide feedback to strengthen the services and gain ownership.

Retaining talent

Research institutions need to be aware of the demands placed upon early career researchers to advance km-scale models forward, and create incentives designed with the academic system in mind, which rewards publications, winning projects and advancing new lines of research. A balanced allocation of time between these activities and the needed technical activities, would be important to maintain.

About the Project

nextGEMS is a collaborative European project. Funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme, it will tap expertise from fourteen European Nations to develop two next generation (storm-resolving) Earth-system Models. Through breakthroughs in simulation realism, these models will allow us to understand and reliably quantify how the climate will change on a global and regional scale, and how the weather, including its extreme events, will look like in the future.

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